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Integrative-Innovative Model of Socio-Cultural Activities Managers Training: a Conceptual and Analytical View

Abstract: *Introduction.* The relevance of the research at the scientific-theoretical and practical levels is related to the need to introduce scientific and organizational support of an integrative-innovative approach to the process of professional training of students majoring in management of socio-cultural activities. *Purpose and methods.* The purpose of the article is the scientific substantiation and development of theoretical-methodological, conceptual and analytical-applied bases of formation of integrative-innovative educational model of training of managers of socio-cultural activity of Ukraine. Scientific analysis was performed using methods of analysis and synthesis; identification; structural and functional modeling; abstract-logical; calculation and analytical; system (system approach and system analysis); tabular; graphic; trend methods; method of statistical and comparative analysis. *Results.* The article analyzes the current problems of professional competence identification of managers of socio-cultural activities in the subject field of their future profession. Generalizing concepts, status and trends in the specialty “Management of socio-cultural activities” are considered at the general scientific and practical levels. *Conclusions.* Proper and clear understanding of the competence structure and content of training will help determine the role and place of future professionals in the socio-cultural sphere of the country. The scientific novelty lies in the substantiation of the conceptual author’s decision on the integrative-innovative model of socio-cultural education. The practical significance of the research in the scientific and applied results and conclusions of the study,

which will serve as a practical tool for adequate management decisions in the socio-cultural sphere.

Keywords: sociocultural sphere, sociocultural activity, management of socio-cultural activity, methodological approach, model of education, system, process, result.

The world needs people who can combine their thinking, knowledge, capabilities and values in imaginative ways to work with complexity, create wealth and prosperity, tackle intractable social and environmental problems, enrich cultures, and enhance their own wellbeing.

Norman Jackson

1. Introduction

The problem formulation. Modern Ukrainian society is in a complex transformational process of socio-cultural transformations. The relevance of the study is that the humanitarian-development of modern Ukrainian society poses new challenges to the domestic education system, the solution of which within the existing methodology is not effective. The high degree of the problem relevance is also confirmed by the fact that many researchers today turn to the analysis of higher education systems and its compliance in the field of training socio-cultural professionals in real-time and changing processes in social and cultural spheres of society. The dependence of the functioning competitiveness of higher education institutions of Ukraine on the transformational educational processes requires initiative actions to design mechanisms for radical reform of the entire system of socio-cultural education from all subjects of educational activity. Transformation processes affecting all aspects of the country's life raise before the education system the issue of the educational model changing, which will expand the concept of humanitarian training.

At the scientific and theoretical level, the relevance of the study is related to the need to implement scientific and organizational support for an integrative and innovative approach to the process of students professional training in "Management of socio-cultural activities". In turn, the scientific and organizational support of the integrative-innovative approach to the professional training of students provides a scientific and methodological level of this problem relevance.

The inconsistency of scientific-theoretical and scientific-practical levels of future specialists training for the socio-cultural sphere of Ukraine identified the problem of research in general, its importance and relevance to improve the educational process.

State study of the problem. As a result of the defined information base elaboration on problems of socio-cultural education of Ukraine, and also, proceeding from results of the statistical analysis of preparation by establishments of higher education of Ukraine of experts for socio-cultural sphere and its

resource (professional) demand, it became more convincing the awareness of the necessity of development and substantiation to create a new educational model of training in the field of socio-cultural activities, which would be updated, supplemented and enriched at the substantive, technological, structural-logical and functional levels.

O. Shcherbyna-Yakovleva (2017) emphasizes the need, first of all, a logical and reasoned definition of the concept of socio-cultural activities, which is a necessary theoretical and methodological basis for the organization of the educational process in cultural areas.

The works of scholars on socio-cultural activities and training in higher education institutions such as Yu. Aliushina et al. (2000), N. Baklanova (2003), O. Chernyshenko (2008), V. Chizhikov, (2003), T. Kemerova and I. Murzina (2019), T. Kiseleva and Yu. Krasilnikov (2004), N. Kochubei (2015), V. Lokshyn (2011, 2013), A. Markov and G. Birzheniuk (1997), Ya. Martynyshyn (2017), I. Petrova (2007), V. Rusavska et al. (2018), O. Shcherbyna-Yakovleva (2017), T. Spirina (2005), G. Tulchinskii and E. Shekova (2009), N. Yaroshenko (2007), E. Zhdanova, S. Ivanov and N. Krotova (2003) and others are of particular value.

In the works of modern Ukrainian and foreign scientists T. Andriushchenko (2013), R. Darmits (2020), F. Levchenko (2020), V. Lokshyn (2011, 2013), O. Ovcharuk (2004), J. Raven (2002) the concept of the competence approach in education is defined, the main categories are formulated and the principles of its introduction are outlined.

The works of I. Bolotnikov and G. Tulchinskii (2007), T. Dmytrenko (2013), G. Galutckii (2001), A. Karpuhin (1998), N. Kirillova (2012), H. Leshchuk (2019), A. Markov and G. Birzheniuk (1997), Ya. Martynyshyn (2017), G. Novikova, (2013), O. Olenina (2013), M. Poplavskiy (1996), A. Zharkov (2013) and others are devoted to the problem's development of the managerial direction training specialists in socio-cultural activities.

Among foreign scholars, the works of I. Adizes (2018), P. Drucker (2004), M. Woodcock and D. Francis (1991), etc. are devoted to the study of the peculiarities of managerial work and higher management education.

The end of the 20th and the beginning of the 21st century became a decisive stage in the scientific substantiation of the essence and content of socio-cultural activities. Representatives of various scientific schools and established practices of the socio-cultural sphere came to understand the essential characteristics of socio-cultural activities and brought the theoretical categorical apparatus, concepts and competency models to a certain methodological justification.

Regularities of socio-cultural activity were determined, which are based on humanistic, creative, initiative beginnings, accumulation and enrichment of society cultural values. These methodological achievements have enriched

the practice and become a reference point in the system of training managers of the socio-cultural sphere and given innovation in the further scientific development of concepts, models, paradigms of socio-cultural education.

Unresolved issues. Despite the increased interest of scientists in the problems of socio-cultural activities and a significant amount of theoretical and applied research on the management of socio-cultural activities, a number of important scientific problems remain unsolved.

In particular, the general concept of the innovative socio-cultural policy of Ukraine needs to be developed, which would be based on equal cooperation of state and business institutions to solve socio-cultural problems in order to improve the quality of life and comprehensive human development. The unresolved problem of formulating a strategy for the development of higher socio-cultural management education at both regional and national levels.

Scientific and practical substantiation of the above-unresolved problems of socio-cultural activities in Ukraine is possible only in cooperation with representatives of science and real practice in the socio-cultural sphere. Such cooperation will further enrich the theory and practice of socio-cultural activities.

2. Purpose and methods

The purpose of the article is scientific substantiation and theoretical-methodological, conceptual and analytical-applied bases development of the formation of the integrative-innovative educational model of managers training of socio-cultural activity in Ukraine.

Achieving this goal caused the need for the study of theoretical, methodical and applied tasks:

- to analyze theoretical and methodological approaches to the formation and functioning of educational models of managers training of socio-cultural activities;
- to conduct a trend analysis of the socio-cultural sphere development of Ukraine and resource (personnel) support of its functioning;
- to propose and substantiate a comprehensive conceptual approach to improving the structural and functional design of the educational model of training managers of socio-cultural activities.

The methodological basis of the study was a set of an interconnected set of theoretical and methodological and scientific and applied aspects of the competence components of functional training, correlation of basic methodological approaches to the educational process, designing of educational models for training managers of socio-cultural activities adequate to today's socio-cultural labour market.

These are the works of domestic and foreign scientists in the field of socio-cultural activities; methods, concepts, techniques and cognition's means of theories of sociocultural activity management; economic laws and patterns; scientific and applied approaches to the study of key aspects of the educational model formation for training managers of socio-cultural activities.

The productive factor of the study also ensured the use of the following principles: objectivity; systematicity; reproducibility; historicism (specifically historical); information sufficiency; adequacy; polysubjectivity; initiative development; innovation.

Research methods. The research methodology is also based on a number of scientific methods. The choice of methods meets the requirements of the real conditions of the study.

These methods are: *analysis and synthesis* are for the study of domestic and world experience in the formation and use of educational systems for training managers, as well as in determining the essential features of the components of the management socio-cultural education system of Ukraine; *theoretical analysis* is to analyze existing views on the research problem (the essence of the socio-cultural activities concept, the role and functional purpose of the manager of socio-cultural activities, modern approaches to the problem of socio-cultural activities managers training, etc.); *abstract-logical* is for the formation of conclusions and theoretical and methodological generalization of research results; system approach and system analysis are in the study of the functions and principles of the educational system of socio-cultural activities managers training, for designing a theoretical conceptual educational model for training managers of socio-cultural activities; *statistical and comparative analysis*, which allowed to objectively assess the level and dynamics of educational processes in Ukraine for the training of managers of socio-cultural activities and the functioning of the socio-cultural sphere of the country; *computational and analytical* to diagnose deviations in the functioning of socio-cultural education in accordance with the dynamics of socio-cultural development; *identification* is in determining the purpose and role of the manager of socio-cultural activities in the management system of socio-cultural organizations; *structural and functional modelling* are in the design of a conceptual educational model of the manager of socio-cultural activities; tabular is for a more rational, visual display of statistical data on the functioning of the socio-cultural sphere in the system of the national economy of Ukraine and the domestic system of management socio-cultural education; graphic is to visualize the generalization, grouping and systematization of analytical statistical material on the dynamics of the socio-cultural sphere of Ukraine; trends method in the analysis of the dynamics of the competitive sets for the speciality

028 “Management of socio-cultural activities”, the dynamics of economic entities of the socio-cultural sphere and the population employed in them, in forecasting trends in the further development of the socio-cultural sphere.

Research information base base of the study included works of domestic and foreign scientists, materials of state statistics of Ukraine for the period 2012-2020, laws of Ukraine, laws and regulations governing educational activities in Ukraine, expert assessments and forecasts of world leaders on trends in education in the 21st century, materials of scientific periodicals on the management of the sociocultural activity, official resources of the Internet in the field of the researched problem, and also results of own researches at preparation and realization of educational programs of bachelor and master levels on a speciality 028 “Management of socio-cultural activity” and when conducting an examination of the accreditation of the educational program in the relevant speciality in higher education establishments of Ukraine.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Theoretical and methodological approaches to the development of models for socio-cultural managers training

The term “socio-cultural activity” should be considered in three senses: as a social practice, which involves many professions of socio-cultural direction today, which are extremely important for the modern socio-cultural sphere; as a branch of scientific knowledge, the theory of which evolves in its development, thanks to the efforts of scientists and practitioners; as an academic discipline that forms a professional with a high level of culture, erudition, with the ability to act in a difficult socio-economic situation and the requirements of the market environment (Kochubei, 2015).

It should also be noted that so far there is no clear and generally accepted meaning of the concept of socio-cultural activities, there is no accurate idea of the subject field of this speciality and professional activity. Therefore, it is important to understand the essence and content of the concept of “socio-cultural activities”.

T. Spirina (2005) interprets socio-cultural activities as a set of scientific, intellectual, artistic, aesthetic and other activities, where the most actively concentrated and effective is the formation of value orientations of young people. The author also notes that socio-cultural activities are designed to ensure a stable balance between social and cultural, as cultural backwardness from constant social change leads to disorganization of life (pp. 139-141).

N. Kochubei (2015) also considers socio-cultural activities from the standpoint of two aspects: cultural and social, defining that socio-cultural activity are a certain system of actions that reflects the functions and objectives of public policy in the field of culture and leisure, identifies ways, methods and means of their implementation is a process driven by society and its social institutions to involve people in culture and the active involvement of human him/herself in this process (p. 17).

H. Leshchuk (2019), considering socio-cultural activities through the prism of socio-educational impact on the individual and summarizing and accumulating all relevant interpretations of this concept in this aspect, argues that socio-cultural activities are a qualitatively new level of human use of their abilities and capabilities in the creation of cultural values and are aimed at the personal development of the individual through the assimilation of a certain system of knowledge, norms, patterns and values (p. 100).

In general, we can distinguish between theoretical (generally scientific) and practical approaches to socio-cultural activities.

General scientific approach. The theory of socio-cultural activity is a rather new direction of research; its conceptual apparatus is still in the process of formation. The very term “socio-cultural activity” entered the scientific and educational circulation only at the end of the twentieth century. The theory of socio-cultural activity began its categorical apparatus with a wide range of humanities (philosophy, cultural theory, sociology of culture, the psychology of culture, etc.). Theoretical developments have formed the methodological foundations of the categorical apparatus and identified a number of different methodological approaches and paradigms in their analysis. Such a diversity of scientific views must be methodologically synthesized in order to understand the essence of socio-cultural activities.

The practical approach to the research problem is based on the analysis of the actual state of training of specialists in socio-cultural activities of Ukraine and on the assessment of the socio-cultural sphere as a component of the national economy of Ukraine.

Currently, the concept of “socio-cultural activities” has official status. In accordance with the Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, a new speciality was approved and departments of socio-cultural activities in higher education establishments of Ukraine were opened, and specialists in the speciality “Management of socio-cultural activities” are actively trained.

Management of socio-cultural activities is a new direction of scientific knowledge, which is rapidly developing and acquiring new concepts and approaches.

The professional purpose of the manager of socio-cultural activities is to carry out functional and official activities of various areas of socio-cultural

activities: show business management, festival management, tourism management, audiovisual management, media management and more.

In the process of performing the official duties, the manager of socio-cultural activities performs the following functions (Novikova, 2013, pp. 140-142):

- organizational and managerial – the formation of institutions goals, the choice of means and methods to achieve goals, the distribution of responsibilities among subordinates, combining them into working groups, control;
- design and technology – research, analytical, forecasting activities for the development and implementation of projects in the field of culture and art;
- communicative – informational interaction in various spheres of public socio-cultural practice, the formation of business and informal relations;
- marketing – conducting research to identify consumers of socio-cultural services and determine the age interests of this audience, market segmentation;
- financial and economic – development of business plans, search for investors, sale of services of socio-cultural organizations in the market.

Management in the socio-cultural sphere covers various areas of management: state cultural policy and legal sphere; interaction of culture and market; practical bases of culture management; managing of various spheres of social and cultural activity (publishing activity, library management system, museum activity, music show business, tourism, TV and radio broadcasting, film production and film distribution, production of multimedia products, etc.). New technologies are internet marketing and online advertising also in the object of management today.

Management of socio-cultural activities is a special multifaceted field of activity that requires a specialist in-depth knowledge not only of the creative process in the system of socio-cultural activities but also media culture, economics, computer science, political science, sociology, the psychology of law, PR-technologies (Kirillova, 2012).

Almost all of these approaches are based on a new socio-cultural concept of general management theory. Within this concept, management is seen as an accurate and humanistic science, which is characterized by a pronounced interdisciplinary nature.

Based on the above, management in socio-cultural activities is an integrative system that combines the policy of the state, market mechanisms and the creative potential of specific teams and individuals.

Accordingly, a specialist in the management of socio-cultural activities is a versatile personality, and its role is to ensure the effectiveness of socio-cultural enterprises by combining managerial, economic, socio-psychological and communicative qualities.

All this poses new challenges for higher education to train professionals capable of working in related fields in the 21st century. Adequate competence set of future specialists will provide an opportunity to carry out socio-cultural modernization of Ukraine.

The speciality “Management of socio-cultural activities” first appeared at the official level of the state at the beginning of the 21st century, respectively, the first enrollment of students in this speciality was carried out. Thus, in June 2005, the Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine dated 16.06.2005 № 363 (Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, 2005) amended the List of areas and specialities for which specialists are trained in higher education establishments according to the relevant educational and qualification levels, approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of May 24, 1997, № 507 (507-97-n) (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 1997), in accordance with which to the section “Culture and Art” direction of training 0201 “Culture” it was introduced the speciality “Management of socio-cultural activities” educational and qualification levels “Bachelor” – 6.020100, “Specialist” – 7.020108 “Master” – 8.020108.

According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine of April 29, 2015, № 266 (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2015). On approval of the list of branches of knowledge and specialities for which higher education is provided speciality “Management of socio-cultural activities” received a new round of development in terms of knowledge 02 “Culture and Art” under code 028.

Applicants’ training for higher education in the speciality 028 “Management of socio-cultural activities” in higher education establishments of Ukraine is carried out according to educational programs developed and approved by higher education establishments in accordance with the approved standards of higher education at the bachelor’s level (Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine 20.06.2019 № 870 (Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, 2019)) and Master (Order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine 08.01.2020 № 14), 2020)). Accordingly, it will be expedient to analyze the dynamics of competitive selection in the speciality 028 “Management of socio-cultural activities” and the regional distribution of higher education establishments that currently train applicants in the relevant speciality. The analysis of the dynamics of competitive sets of applicants for higher education for the speciality 028 “Management of socio-cultural activities” in Ukraine in the period 2018-2020 is presented in *Table 1*.

Despite the rather large number of bids in the speciality 028 “Management of socio-cultural activities” (which, as can be seen from *Table 1* and given the projected increase in 2020, tends to annual stable growth), the actual number of educational programs for which applicants are trained in the speciality is almost similar to the number of higher education establishments.

Table 1. Dynamics of competitive sets of applicants for higher education for the speciality 028 “Management of socio-cultural activities” in Ukraine in the period 2018-2020

Name of indicators	Dynamics of sets by educational degrees					
	Bachelor			Master		
	2018	2019	2020*	2018	2019	2020*
Number of higher education establishments that recruited	21	23	18	10	11	9
Number of bids ** (including full-time and part-time study, open, closed and non-budget proposals)	62	86	28	31	38	15
Number of educational programs	23	25	20	12	13	10
Number of specializations	4	6	6	5	6	5

* as of March 2020, taking into account all proposals registered in the system. At the beginning of the introductory campaign in 2020, the values of the indicators will certainly increase due to the registration of a significant number of non-budget proposals, in particular in private higher education establishments, which is projected to exceed the indicators for previous periods;

** competitive offer is an offer of a higher education establishment for admission of entrants to a certain speciality.

Source: own development on the basis of Information System “Osvita.ua” (<https://vstup.osvita.ua/>)

This indicates that almost all higher education establishments that carried out the recruitment, within one level of higher education have one characteristic educational program in the speciality 028 “Management of socio-cultural activities”, and only in two institutions of higher education (Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts and Private Higher Educational Institution “Kyiv University of Culture”) at one level of higher education carry out the preparation of applicants for the speciality simultaneously in several educational programs – such a phenomenon is characteristic of both the first (bachelor’s) and second (master’s) levels of higher education.

The analysis of the selected specializations diversity in terms of speciality 028 “Management of socio-cultural activities” for the first and second levels of education in the period from 2018-2020 was conducted on the basis of the analysis of competitive proposals of higher education establishments in a certain period and presented in *Table 2*.

Table 2. Educational programs, distinguished in terms of speciality 028 “Management of socio-cultural activities” for the first and second levels of education in the period from 2018-2020

Educational programs	Distribution of the number of educational programs by educational degrees					
	Bachelor			Master		
	2018	2019	2020	2018	2019	2020
Management of socio-cultural activities	15	14	13	7	7	6
Management of hotel and restaurant and tourist business	6	7	3	2	2	1
Art management	1	1	1	1	1	1
Management of socio-cultural projects	–	–	–	1	1	1
Leisure industry management (hotel, tourist, recreational)	–	1	–	–	–	–
Culture management and social marketing	1	–	–	–	–	–
Occasion management	–	–	–	1	–	1
Event management	–	1	–	–	1	–
Culture management	–	1	1	–	–	–
Cross-cultural management	–	–	–	–	1	–
Show business management	–	–	1	–	–	–
Fashion business management	–	–	1	–	–	–

Source: development on the basis of Information System “Osvita.ua” (<https://vstup.osvita.ua/>)

Regarding the variety of specializations, it should be noted that, as can be seen from *Table 1*, their number within each year of recruitment is very small, and in general for the period 2018-2020 recruitment for speciality 028 “Management of socio-cultural activities” is 12 specializations (called by the educational program). Based on the analysis presented in *Table 2*, it is seen that the lion’s share of all specializations in the name of educational programs is directly occupied by the management of socio-cultural activities without any clarifications and ramifications.

Separate specializations are mostly isolated within a particular institution of higher education and are unique in other educational institutions, which indicates a kind of uniqueness of such educational programs and applicants who master them.

Accordingly, there is a need for a regional analysis of the applicants training for the speciality 028 “Management of socio-cultural activities” in Ukraine, which is presented in *Table 3*.

Table 3. Distribution of training of specialists in management of socio-cultural activities in higher education establishments by regions of Ukraine as of March 2020

Region	Number of educational institutions that train applicants in the specialty 028			
	Total	by educational degrees		
		Associate Degree	Bachelor	Master
city of Kyiv	6	2	4	4
Vinnyska region	1	1	–	–
Volynska region	–	–	–	–
Dnipropetrovska region	1	–	1	–
Donetska region	–	–	–	–
Zhytomyrska region	1	1	–	–
Zakarpatska region	1	–	1	–
Zaporizka region	1	1	–	–
Ivano-Frankivska region	3	1	2	–
Kyivska region	–	–	–	–
Kirovohradska region	1	1	–	–
Luhanska region	–	–	–	–
Lvivska region	5	2	3	1
Mykolaivska region	1	–	1	–
Odeska region	1	–	1	–
Poltavska region	2	1	1	–
Rivnenska region	2	1	1	1
Sumska region	3	1	2	1
Ternopilska region	3	1	2	1
Kharkivska region	2	–	1	2
Khersonska region	–	–	–	–
Khmelnyska region	1	1	–	–
Cherkaska region	2	1	1	–
Chernivetska region	–	–	–	–
Chernihivska region	2	1	1	–
Total	39	17	22	10

Source: own development on the basis of The Only State Electronic Database on Education (<https://registry.edbo.gov.ua/>)

The data presented in *Table 3* show that in general in Ukraine the training of specialists in the speciality 028 “Management of socio-cultural activities” is carried out by 39 educational institutions, among which the second level of higher education (Master’s degree) is provided by 10 higher education institutions, which is 25%, (Bachelor’s degree) – 22 institutions of higher education (56%). Currently there is no practice of training applicants of the third level of education (Doctor of philosophy) at all. Considering the regional aspect of training specialists in the speciality 028 “Management of socio-cultural activities”, it should be noted that training at the second (master’s) level of higher education is carried out only in 6 regions of Ukraine. The largest number of higher education institutions is the city of Kyiv (4 institutions of higher education, which is 40%), training of applicants for the first (bachelor’s level) of higher education is carried out in 14 out of 25 regions of Ukraine. That is, slightly less than half (44%) of the regions of the state do not train their “own” managers of socio-cultural activities, even at the first bachelor’s level of higher education.

3.2. Development trends analysis of the socio-cultural sphere of Ukraine and staffing of its functioning

To understand the specifics of the speciality “Management of socio-cultural activities” it is necessary to determine the subject field of their professional activities, to specify the scope of their professional skills and abilities. Such a sphere is the socio-cultural sphere.

In scientific circulation, the term “socio-cultural sphere” began to be approved in the early 1980s. The spread of the term is a natural process, as material production, fulfilling its historical role, gave way to leadership in the service sector in general and to meeting the socio-cultural needs of society in particular. All over the world, the attention of scientists and businesses to the production of such services is increasing.

In the 21st century, the socio-cultural sphere is an important sector of the Ukrainian economy, which is a dynamically developing, independent economic system of various enterprises and organizations specializing in the production of goods and services of socio-cultural orientation.

Considering the socio-cultural sphere from the standpoint of the national economy of Ukraine through the prism of the list of sections and industries that it includes, it should be noted that the socio-cultural sphere is an important component of the service sector of Ukraine and in accordance with the general economic structure defined in the classifier of economic activities (NACE DK 009: 2010), fully or partially includes 8 of the 12 sections related to the service sector. A broad analysis of the content of the socio-cultural sphere is presented in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1. Filling the socio-cultural sphere in accordance with the general economic structure defined in the Classifier of economic activities DK 009:2010

Source: own development on the basis of (State Statistics Committee of Ukraine, 2011)

The economic significance and importance of each section in the overall structure of the socio-cultural sphere, services and the national economy of Ukraine as a whole can be traced by analyzing the number of businesses and employees, as well as tracking the dynamics of these indicators over the past seven years (2012-2018).

The dynamics of the total number of economic entities in the socio-cultural sphere in relation to their number in the service sector and Ukraine as a whole in the period 2012-2018 is presented in *Figure 2*.

Figure 2. Dynamics of the total number of economic entities in the socio-cultural sphere in relation to their number in the service sector and Ukraine as a whole in the period 2012-2018

Source: own development on the basis of State Statistics Service of Ukraine (<http://www.ukrstat.gov.ua/>)

Analyzing the data presented in *Figure 2*, it should be noted that despite the rather wide range of sectoral content of the socio-cultural sphere, the number of business entities that are officially registered within the socio-cultural sphere in the structure of the national economy of Ukraine is quite small and in different periods ranges from 11.5% to 15% in relation to the total number of business entities in Ukraine, and respectively in the range of 13.5-17.5% in relation to their number in the service sector. However, the positive thing is that the number of economic entities in the socio-cultural sphere in the period 2012-2018 tends to grow annually in both quantitative and percentage terms, which cannot be said about their total number in Ukraine as a whole and in particular in the non-productive sector of the national economy, a component of which is the socio-cultural sphere:

– 2012-2015 – annual growth of the number of enterprises in Ukraine in general and in the sphere of services in particular in relation to the previous year by 8%, 12% and 2% respectively;

– 2016-2017 – reduction of the total number of enterprises in Ukraine and in particular in the sphere of services in relation to the previous year by 5% and 3% respectively;

– 2018 – the growth of the number of business entities in the domestic economic system in general and services in particular by 2%.

In order to identify the most promising and most progressive industries (sections) of the socio-cultural sphere in Ukraine by the number of enterprises, it is necessary to analyze the number of economic entities in the socio-cultural sphere in terms of each section (*Table 4*).

In order to improve the visualization and clarity of the data presented in *Table 4*, we present them in the form of a graph showing the dynamics of changes in the number of socio-cultural entities in terms of individual economic activities in 2012-2018 (*Figure 3*).

Analyzing the dynamics of changes in the number of economic entities in the socio-cultural sphere in terms of certain economic activities in the period 2012-2018 (*Table 4, Figure 3*), we can say that the most important and most numerous sectors of the socio-cultural sphere are “Temporary accommodation and organization nutrition (div. 55, 56)”, “Information and telecommunications (div. 58, 59, 60, 61, 63)”, “Professional, scientific and technical activities (div. 72, 73, 74)” and “Provision of other services (div. 96)”, which in total in different years make up from 83.7 to 84.9% of the total number of enterprises in the socio-cultural sphere. In quantitative and percentage terms, the trend towards stable annual growth in the period 2012-2018 is observed in two of them:

– “Information and telecommunications (div. 58, 59, 60, 61, 63)” – the number of business entities in units increased by 1.75 times, as a percentage – by 2.3%;

– “Provision of other types of services (div. 96)” – growth in units by 1.7 times, as a percentage – by 3.4%.

The industry “Temporary accommodation and catering (div. 55, 56)” has the trend of annual growth in the number of enterprises in units in the period 2012-2018. Its importance in a certain indicator in 2018 increased compared to 2012 by 1.3 times, however, in percentage terms it decreased by 1.7%.

“Professional, scientific and technical activities (div. 72, 73, 74)” although currently one of the “leading industries” in the number of economic entities in the socio-cultural sphere, but in recent years, both quantitatively and in percentage terms significantly weakens their positions: a decrease in 2018 in units compared to the highest value (2015) by 1.17 times, and in percentage – by 5%.

The other three sections such as “Activities in the field of administrative and support services (div. 78, 79)”, “Education (div. 85)” and “Arts, sports, entertainment and recreation (div. 90, 91, 92, 93)” tend to the so-called “equally stable development”, varying the values of the indicator within 5% each, i.e. the total weight of these three industries is within 15%. The least numerous

Table 4. The number of economic entities in the socio-cultural sphere in relation to their number in the service sector and Ukraine as a whole in the period 2012-2018

Sector	Number of business entities	Distribution of the business entities number by years						
		2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
	TOTAL in Ukraine	1600304	1722251	1932325	1974439	1865631	1805144	1839672
	Including in the field of services	1366949 85.4 % ¹	1476966 85.8 % ¹	1672985 86.6 % ¹	1704878 86.3 % ¹	1613734 86.5 % ¹	1554414 86.1 % ¹	1584954 86.2 % ¹
	Including in the socio-cultural sphere	184183 11.5% ¹ 13.5%*	210127 12.2% ¹ 14.2%*	239539 12.4% ¹ 14.3%*	247500 12.5% ¹ 14.5%*	241063 12.9% ¹ 14.9%*	255532 14.2% ¹ 16.4%*	277612 15.1% ¹ 17.5%*
I	Temporary accommodation and catering (div. 55, 56)	44085 23.9%**	52077 24.8%**	57553 24.0%**	58436 23.6%**	57696 23.9%**	57578 22.5%**	61761 22.2%**
J	Information and telecommunications (div. 58, 59, 60, 61, 63)	25972 14.1%**	30359 14.4%**	36106 15.1%**	36479 14.7%**	37922 15.7%**	40368 15.8%**	45556 16.4%**
M	Professional, scientific and technical activities (div. 72, 73, 74)	37401 20.3%**	42909 20.4%**	49477 20.7%**	51704 20.9%**	47114 19.5%**	43734 17.1%**	44111 15.9%**
N	Activities in the field of administrative and support services (div. 78, 79)	10362 5.6%**	11884 5.7%**	12512 5.2%**	11823 4.8%**	12462 5.2%**	12933 5.1%**	13680 4.9%**
P	Education (div. 85)	7317 4.0%**	8467 4.0%**	10117 4.2%**	10873 4.4%**	11077 4.6%**	11656 4.6%**	13241 4.8%**
Q	Health care and social assistance (div. 88)	910 0.5%**	1043 0.5%**	1452 0.6%**	1674 0.7%**	1895 0.8%**	2072 0.8%**	2403 0.9%**
R	Arts, sports, entertainment and recreation (div. 90, 91, 92, 93)	9238 5.0%**	11620 5.5%**	13523 5.6%**	14887 6.0%**	13873 5.8%**	13045 5.1%**	13797 5.0%**
S	Provision of other types of services (div. 96)	48898 26.5%**	51768 24.6%**	58799 24.5%**	61624 24.9%**	59024 24.5%**	74146 29.0%**	83063 29.9%**

¹ – in % to the total number of business entities in Ukraine;

* – in % to the number of business entities in the service sector;

** – in % to the number of business entities in the socio-cultural sphere;

Source: own development on the basis of State Statistics Service of Ukraine (<http://www.ukrstat.gov.ua/>)

Figure 3. Dynamics of the number of economic entities in the socio-cultural sphere in terms of certain types of economic activity in the period 2012-2018 (in quantity and in% to the total amount in SCS)
 Source: own development on the basis of State Statistics Service of Ukraine (<http://www.ukrstat.gov.ua/>)

in the number of business entities in the socio-cultural sphere is the part of section Q, namely – division 88 “Provision of social assistance without accommodation”. However, it should be noted that during 2012-2018, this industry has a tendency to gradual but stable growth in both quantitative and percentage terms, increasing its position by 2.6 times (in units) and by 0.5%.

Analysis of the dynamics of changes in the number of economic entities in the socio-cultural sphere and the identification of its trends in this indicator requires the analysis of another indicator, no less important for understanding the priority and direction in forming an integrative conceptual model of in-demand specialists training in the sphere of socio-cultural activities – the number of the employed population in the economic entities of the socio-cultural sphere. The dynamics of the total number of the employed population in economic entities in the socio-cultural sphere in relation to their number in the service sector and Ukraine as a whole in the period 2012-2018 is presented in *Figure 4*.

Figure 4. Dynamics of the total number of employed population in economic entities in the socio-cultural sphere in relation to their number in the service sector and Ukraine as a whole in the period 2012-2018

Source: own development on the basis of State Statistics Service of Ukraine (<http://www.ukrstat.gov.ua>)

Analyzing the data presented in *Figure 4* and comparing them with the dynamics of changes in the number of economic entities (*Figure 2*) in the same period of time, it should be noted that the dynamics of changes in the number of employed in economic entities in Ukraine as a whole, services and the socio-cultural sphere has a reverse trend. The number of employed persons in business entities in Ukraine in general in the period 2012-2017 tends to decrease steadily annually (compared to 2012 in 2017, the number of the employed population decreased by more than 1.9 million people, which is 18.9 %) and only in 2018, there is a slight increase in this value by about 390 thousand people, which as a percentage of 2017 is 4.71%. A similar picture is characteristic for both the services sector and the socio-cultural sphere: in 2012-2016, the dynamics of decrease by slightly more than 848 thousand people (14.63%) and 138 thousand people (16.5%) was observed, respectively; in 2017-2018, the number of employed population gradually increased annually over the two years by 455.5 thousand people (9.2%) and 52.6 thousand people (7.53%), respectively. A similar picture is characteristic for both the services sector and the socio-cultural sphere: in 2012-2016, the dynamics of decrease by slightly more than 848 thousand people (14.63%) and 138 thousand people (16.5%) was observed, respectively. In 2017-2018, there was a gradual annual increase in the number of the employed population over two years by 455.5 thousand people (9.2%) and 52.6 thousand people (7.53%), respectively.

At the same time, the number of the employed population in economic entities of the socio-cultural sphere in the structure of the national economy of Ukraine in different periods ranges from 8.22% to 8.69% in relation to the total number of economic entities in Ukraine, and respectively within 13.8% – 14.5% in relation to their number in the services sector.

The analysis of the number of the employed population in the subjects of the socio-cultural sphere in the context of each individual section is presented in the form of *Table 5*.

Table 5. The number of employees in economic entities in the socio-cultural sphere in relation to their number in the service sector and Ukraine as a whole in the period 2012-2018

Section	Number of employees in business entities	Distribution of the number of employees by economic entities by years						
		2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
	TOTAL in Ukraine	10198733	9965076	9008271	8331931	8244025	8271338	8661298
	Including in the field of services	5797903 56.8% ¹	5735510 57.6% ¹	5350062 59.4% ¹	4989017 59.9% ¹	4949806 60.0% ¹	5007700 60.5% ¹	5405348 62.4% ¹
	Including in the socio-cultural sphere	838330 8.22% ¹ 14.5%*	826870 8.30% ¹ 14.4%*	738104 8.19% ¹ 13.8%*	709449 8.51% ¹ 14.2%*	700030 8.49% ¹ 14.1%*	709096 8.57% ¹ 14.2%*	752712 8.69% ¹ 13.9%*
I	Temporary accommodation and catering (div. 55, 56)	264284 31.5%**	267487 32.3%**	213197 28.9%**	195194 27.5%**	207863 29.7%**	224220 31.6%**	269741 35.8%**
J	Information and telecommunications (div. 58, 59, 60, 61, 63)	206610 24.6%**	189689 22.9%**	165792 22.5%**	170147 24.0%**	157138 22.4%**	140535 19.8%**	115745 15.4%**
M	Professional, scientific and technical activities (div. 72, 73, 74)	135644 16.2%**	134249 16.2%**	126537 17.1%**	120483 17.0%**	114496 16.4%**	112469 15.9%**	114382 15.2%**
N	Activities in the field of administrative and support services (div. 78, 79)	43323 5.2%**	46547 5.6%**	55554 7.5%**	48634 6.9%**	49238 7.0%**	46427 6.5%**	46652 6.2%**
P	Education (div. 85)	34385 4.1%**	33847 4.1%**	31024 4.2%**	30734 4.3%**	30746 4.4%**	32040 4.5%**	34382 4.6%**
Q	Health care and social assistance (div. 88)	1008 0.1%**	1122 0.1%**	1569 0.2%**	1852 0.3%**	2145 0.3%**	2547 0.4%**	3154 0.4%**
R	Arts, sports, entertainment and recreation (div. 90, 91, 92, 93)	49539 5.9%**	51771 6.3%**	47769 6.5%**	48859 6.9%**	46129 6.6%**	45149 6.4%**	49414 6.6%**
S	Provision of other types of services (div. 96)	103537 12.4%**	102158 12.4%**	96662 13.1%**	93546 13.2%**	92275 13.2%**	105709 14.9%**	119242 15.8%**

¹ – in % to the total number of the employed population of business entities in Ukraine;

* – in % to the number of the employed population in business entities;

** – in % to the number of the employed population in economic entities of the socio-cultural sphere

Source: own development on the basis of State Statistics Service of Ukraine

(<http://www.ukrstat.gov.ua/>)

Graphical analysis of *Table 5* data is presented in *Figure 5*.

Figure 5. Dynamics of the number of employed population in the economic entities of the socio-cultural sphere in terms of certain types of economic activity in the period 2012-2018 (in the number of persons and in % to the total number in the socio-cultural sphere)

Source: own development on the basis of State Statistics Service of Ukraine (<http://www.ukrstat.gov.ua/>)

Based on the analysis of the dynamics of changes in the number of the employed population in economic entities in the socio-cultural sphere in terms of certain economic activities in the period 2012-2018 (*Table 5*, *Figure 5*), it should be noted that the four “leading industries” compared to the number economic entities, remained unchanged and its total part in different years ranged from 81.6% to 84.7% of the total number of employed people in the enterprises of the socio-cultural sphere. However, places and trends in it look a little different. The branch “Temporary accommodation and caterin” (div. 55, 56) is the most important in terms of number and percentage and one that has continued to grow in recent years. Its value according to a certain indicator in 2018 compared to 2012 (according to various indicators defined as one of

the most promising in the development of the industry) after falling in 2013-2015 (by 27 thousand people – 24.03%) increased by almost 5.5 thousand persons and by 2.1%. It should also be noted that the volume of this industry in terms of the number of the employed population in 2018 reached 35.8%, although in terms of the number of enterprises in the same period it was 22.2%.

It is also worth noting that the section “Information and Telecommunications (div. 58, 59, 60, 61, 63)”, despite the dynamic and stable growth of the number of business entities in the period 2012-2018, in the number of employees as in quantitative and percentage terms has a completely reverse trend and its indicators in 2018 compared to 2012 decreased almost twice by more than 90 thousand people and lost 9.3% of its weight on this indicator in the overall structure of the socio-cultural sphere.

Numerical and percentage significance of the section “Provision of other types of services (div. 96)” in the period 2012-2016 is characterized by predominant stability, fluctuating between 12-13% and improving its position in 2017-2018 by about 27 thousand people, thus increasing its weight to 15.8%.

Section “Professional, scientific and technical activities (div. 72, 73, 74)” both in terms of the number of business entities in the socio-cultural sphere and the number of their population in recent years, both in quantitative and percentage terms significantly weakens its position: a decrease in 2018 in units compared to the largest value (2012) by more than 22 thousand people, while losing more than 1% of its importance for the socio-cultural sphere.

Summing up the analysis of the dynamics of changes in the number of economic entities in the socio-cultural sphere and their employed population, it should be noted that taking into account its results should be one of the important components in determining the conceptual features and narrowly specialized areas in the formation of educational models of specialists’ training in socio-cultural activities in higher education establishments of Ukraine.

In general, the socio-cultural sphere is on the rise, showing a growing trend in the number of businesses that are in the process of internationalization and transnationalization of economic activity, which, in turn, requires staffing with the necessary competency to be formed in the learning process.

3.3. Conceptual approach to designing a modern model of training managers of socio-cultural activities

The set of future professional competencies must fully correspond to the functional areas of formation of specialists of a certain profile. And these are organizational and managerial, design and technological, financial and economic, legal, marketing, communication. These requirements should be reflected

in educational programs, curricula, as well as in forms, methods and modern learning technologies.

Due to globalization and the definition of the constant variability of the external environment, it can be argued that today there is no unambiguous definition of professional competencies of graduates of higher education establishments. The concept of professional competence is associated with the production functions that are provided in the professional activity. Their design requires joint cooperation of higher education establishments, business, society and the state.

There is also no universal algorithm for forming a model of professional competencies. Each institution of higher education has its own specifics of training. In the conditions when there is a dynamic development of new technologies, continuous technical re-equipment of modern productions, business more and more demands not to concrete knowledge, but to competencies of workers.

Now the business of socio-cultural sphere in the selection of personnel and in solving organizational and production problems does not rely only on their intuition but uses data from marketing research, effective innovations in modern management, science-based provisions in organizational and corporate culture. This approach of business to the required qualifications of specialists should be taken into account by higher education establishments in the educational model formation of the specialist. Now the business of socio-cultural sphere in the selection of personnel and in solving organizational and production problems does not rely only on their intuition but uses marketing research data, effective innovations in modern management, science-based provisions in the organizational and corporate culture of the enterprise. This approach of business to the required qualifications of specialists should be taken into account by higher education establishments in the formation of the educational model of the specialist.

The problem of a model developing of a specialist is not new for higher education, it is devoted to a lot of research using different conceptual approaches, but variable, transformational educational processes have actualized the problem with new force.

In the works of the above authors, some aspects of managers of socio-cultural activities training are reflected, however, the process of modelling the training of graduates adapted to the labour market of socio-cultural sphere did not find, in our opinion, proper coverage, that highlighted the need to design an integrative and innovative model of socio-cultural activities managers training in Ukraine.

The model of the specialist must meet modern requirements, be flexible, dynamic, viable, have the ability to constantly adjust to changes and requirements for the profession and speciality. "The speed of construction of the

model should be not less than the speed of change of its determining factors” (Aliushina et al., 2000, p. 27).

Ideally, educational models should be created on the basis of strategies for training specialists in socio-cultural activities of management. Since today such a holistic strategy does not exist, the educational model of a specialist in the management of socio-cultural activities should be developed on the basis of methodological approaches:

- competence – adopted as one of the key methodological tools for the modernization of vocational education in Europe. Designing educational programs according to the competency approach means reflecting the results of education in a systematic and holistic way. A competency approach is needed, but it must be balanced by strengthening humanization in the educational activities of higher education establishments;

- humanistic – reorientation of education from the subject-content principle of teaching the basics of science to the study of the value picture of the world and, above all, the world of culture, a man, the formation of humanistic and systemic thinking in youth;

- socio-cultural – contains significant opportunities for the implementation of modern requirements for the education system of the 21st century. It envisages combining the content of education and upbringing of young people into a holistic educational process based on a single goal, common socio-cultural values and technologies of effective learning. It ensures the harmonious development of the student's personality. It develops education as an open organizational system that can become an important unifying factor;

- culturological (value) – is the main method of designing personality-oriented education. The culturological approach in education is a methodological orientation, which in its philosophical basis has an axiological (value) vector of development.

In terms of the necessary interaction of higher education establishments with the real business of socio-cultural sphere, the methodological component of professional adaptation of future professionals should be system-activity and practice-oriented approaches in the process of training (education) of students.

The system-activity approach provides:

- formation of readiness for self-development and continuing education;
- designing the social environment of development (connection with society) in the education system;
- active educational and cognitive activities;
- construction of the educational process taking into account individual features.

A relatively new form in the educational process is a practice-oriented approach to student learning. The practice-oriented approach should be cross-cutting (conceptual) in the training of specialists. Tasks focused on the implementation of real business problems should be introduced from the very beginning of training, which will ensure the aggregation of the learning process and internships, as well as the formation of students' cross-cutting competencies that would ensure the performance of functional responsibilities in the speciality.

The implementation of a practice-oriented approach will provide students with not only practical but also general cultural, social competencies that they need for future professional activities.

“Problem field” dictates the scope of competencies, functions and content of the activities of a specialist working in the socio-cultural sphere, and hence sets the content of his training. This problem is relevant for all stakeholders in the process of training a specialist in the management of socio-cultural activities (state, institutions of higher education, business, society).

The annual session of the World Economic Forum in Davos (2020) proclaimed the “Reskilling Revolution” – an initiative that aims to provide 1 billion people by 2030 better skills, education and jobs (World Economic Forum in Davos, 2020).

When discussing issues of professional development and the future labour market, well-known experts (M. Zuckerberg, J. Soros, B. Gates and others) noted the rapid pace of learning – the change of key professional skills, the reorientation of most future competencies to cognitive nature (related to thinking) (World Economic Forum in Davos, 2020).

The professional model is a wide range of competencies that form the ability to apply knowledge in different areas (management, marketing, finance, economics, people management, etc.) and their in-depth (expert) level, it is functional knowledge and skills.

Regarding the 2020 competency horizon, the World Economic Forum in Davos (2020) ranked among the most important and relevant: critical thinking, creativity, cognitive flexibility (ability to adapt), emotional intelligence, soft skills, customer orientation. This approach requires the creation of a new model of training managers of socio-cultural activities, which would meet the modern requirements of the socio-cultural sphere.

Since, based on the above, socio-cultural education is an extremely complex, multidimensional object that is studied from the standpoint of many sciences, so its conceptual solution for the formation of the model should be multi-aspect and multivariate.

Guaranteeing quality socio-cultural education in the 21st century is possible only on the basis of the principles of integrativeness and innovation – the integration of modern innovative educational systems of education, upbringing and personal development in the process of specialists' training.

The integrative-innovative model of higher Ukrainian socio-cultural education can be presented as a system of theoretical and methodological approaches, models, tools, principles, mechanisms that will ensure the advanced nature of training of socio-cultural education managers.

The synthesizing role in the integrative-innovative educational socio-cultural model of training managers of socio-cultural activities should belong to the value-oriented and multicultural areas, which will be an adequate reflection of the modern market's needs of the socio-cultural sphere.

4. Conclusions

Based on the scientific and methodological principles, basic principles and existing educational models of training managers of socio-cultural activities, as well as the analysis of the socio-cultural sphere in the national economy of Ukraine and the conceptual and analytical view of the current state of training managers of socio-cultural activities in Ukraine, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The purpose and objectives of scientific research are fulfilled. The article presents a conceptual author's view on solving the scientific-applied problem of maintaining a high-quality level of training of managers of socio-cultural activities through the formation of the integration-innovative educational model of training in socio-cultural management, which meets modern requirements and trends of the socio-cultural sphere of Ukraine.

2. A conceptual view on the formation of an integrative-innovative model of higher socio-cultural education training of managers of socio-cultural activities not only actualized the problem points of speciality development but also substantiated their solution in the formation and implementation of an integrative-innovative model of socio-cultural education based on competence approach, which will make it impossible to lag behind the content of the university socio-cultural management education from the needs of practices (domestic and foreign).

3. This conceptual vision requires concretization to the level of organizational and technological mechanism, which must be further implemented in the form of innovative scientific and methodological approaches to improve the practical results of the educational process of training managers of socio-cultural activities.

The scientific novelty of the obtained results is as follows:

– a new theoretical and applied solution for the author’s modification of the model of higher management socio-cultural education on the basis of innovative and integrative approaches to the existing methodological tools in science and the existing bank of educational models is substantiated, which allowed to adapt to modern transformational requirements of educational processes and to achieve a synergistic effect as a result of the training of socio-cultural activities managers;

– the necessity of taking into account the concept of innovative-integrative approach to socio-cultural education on the basis of the competence component as an ideological basis of new educational standards is substantiated, which will make essential qualitative changes in the content of the educational process of training managers of socio-cultural activities;

– the dynamics of “increasing” the importance of socio-cultural, humanistic and civilizational approaches in the educational process is determined, which can become a noticeable applied effect in the development of theory and practice of modern socio-cultural activities management.

The practical significance of the results obtained in the fact that the theoretical provisions of the study were brought to the level of specific methods and recommendations, in particular in:

– scientific and applied results and conclusions of the study, which are a reaction to certain crisis situations in the socio-cultural sphere and which will serve as a practical tool for adequate management decisions on the main problems of the Ukrainian cultural sphere, training “correct” competitive specialists;

– definition of priority directions of the social and cultural activity development of Ukraine defined as possibilities of “practice” of scientific developments for a real subject field of future experts activity.

Prospects for further scientific research in this direction are primarily:

– theoretical and methodological justification for the development of an educational paradigm that would reflect the convergence of modern science and innovative technologies in higher education;

– development of single information space of scientific communication in the field of socio-cultural activities;

– peculiarities of specialists training in socio-cultural management in higher education establishments in accordance with the needs of regional labour markets of the socio-cultural sphere of Ukraine;

– digitalization of the educational process – the use of information educational technologies (digital technologies) during the full educational cycle of socio-cultural activities specialists training.

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